

Original paper

IMPROVING SPELLING LITERACY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS IN NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS

© Aysara D. Najimova¹✉

¹Ajiniyaz Nukus State Pedagogical Institute, Nukus, Karakalpakstan

Annotation

INTRODUCTION: The given article analyzes key aspects of the formation of spelling literacy in primary school learners. An overview of psychological and pedagogical prerequisites and causes of errors is presented, and effective teaching methods that integrate classical and innovative approaches are described. The work contains practical recommendations on lesson planning, a system of exercises, diagnostics and correction, as well as advice on working with parents, addressed to future and practicing primary school teachers.

AIM: The aim of this article is to explore effective pedagogical strategies for improving the spelling literacy of primary school learners in native language lessons, and to identify teaching methods that enhance students' spelling accuracy and written communication skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: This study employed observational analysis, diagnostic tests, and classroom experimentation to assess students' spelling abilities. A variety of teaching approaches were applied, including phonetic exercises, visual dictations, interactive spelling games, and error correction activities. Data was collected before and after applying these methods to measure improvement.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: Findings revealed that systematic use of interactive and visual methods significantly improved students' spelling performance. Learners became more attentive to orthographic patterns, word structures, and the phoneme-grapheme relationship. Repeated practice through engaging activities helped reinforce correct spelling and boosted learners' confidence in written expression.

CONCLUSION Spelling literacy can be effectively improved through the integration of phonetic awareness, repetition, and interactive methods in native language lessons. Tailoring instructional strategies to students' developmental needs plays a key role in strengthening their orthographic competence and overall language proficiency.

Key words: spelling literacy, primary school, native language, young learners, spelling errors, teaching methods, didactics, psychology, pedagogical technologies, correctional work.

For citation: Aysara D. Najimova. (2025) 'Improving spelling literacy of primary school learners in native language lessons', Inter education & global study, (6), pp. 59–66.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОРФОГРАФИЧЕСКОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ НА УРОКАХ РОДНОГО ЯЗЫКА

© А.Д. Наджимова^{1✉}

¹Аджиниёзский Нукусский государственный педагогический институт, Нукус, Каракалпакстан

Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: В данной статье рассматриваются ключевые аспекты формирования орфографической грамотности у учащихся начальных классов. Представлен обзор психологических и педагогических предпосылок, а также причин орфографических ошибок. Описаны эффективные методы обучения, сочетающие классические и инновационные подходы. Работа содержит практические рекомендации по планированию уроков, системе упражнений, диагностике и коррекции, а также советы по взаимодействию с родителями — для будущих и практикующих учителей начальных классов.

ЦЕЛЬ: Целью настоящей статьи является изучение эффективных педагогических стратегий по улучшению орфографической грамотности учащихся начальных классов на уроках родного языка и определение методов обучения, способствующих повышению точности правописания и развитию навыков письменной речи у школьников.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: В исследовании использовались наблюдение, диагностическое тестирование и экспериментальная работа в классе. Применялись различные методы обучения: фонетические упражнения, визуальные диктанты, интерактивные орфографические игры и задания на исправление ошибок. Данные собирались до и после применения методик с целью измерения прогресса.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: Результаты показали, что систематическое использование интерактивных и визуальных методов значительно улучшает орфографические навыки учащихся. Ученики становятся более внимательными к орфографическим закономерностям, структуре слов и соотношению между звуками и буквами. Повторяющаяся практика в игровой форме способствует закреплению правильного написания и повышает уверенность в письменной речи.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: Орфографическую грамотность можно эффективно развивать через интеграцию фонетического восприятия, повторения и интерактивных методов в уроках родного языка. Индивидуально подобранные педагогические стратегии играют важную роль в укреплении орфографических умений и общей языковой компетенции учащихся.

Ключевые слова: орфографическая грамотность, начальная школа, родной язык, младшие школьники, орфографические ошибки, методы обучения, дидактика, психология, педагогические технологии, коррекционная работа.

Для цитирования: Наджимова А.Д. Совершенствование орфографической грамотности учащихся начальной школы на уроках родного языка // Inter education & global study. 2025, №6. С. 59–66.

ONA TILI DARSLARIDA BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARINING IMLO SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH

© A.D. Najimova¹✉

¹Ajiniyoz nomidagi Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti, Nukus, Qoraqalpog'iston

Annotatsiya

KIRISH: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida imlo savodxonligini shakllantirishning asosiy jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. O'quvchilarda uchraydigan xatolarning psixologik va pedagogik sabablari ko'rib chiqiladi hamda klassik va innovatsion yondashuvlarni o'z ichiga olgan samarali o'qitish metodlari yoritiladi. Ishda darslarni rejalashtirish, mashq tizimi, diagnostika va tuzatish ishlari, shuningdek, ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar keltirilgan. Ushbu tavsiyalar bo'lajak va amaldagi boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilariga mo'ljallangan.

MAQSAD: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi — boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ona tili darslarida imlo savodxonligini oshirishga qaratilgan samarali pedagogik strategiyalarni o'rganish hamda o'quvchilarning yozma nutqdagi xatolarsiz yozish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiluvchi o'qitish metodlarini aniqlashdan iborat.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR Tadqiqot davomida kuzatuv tahlili, diagnostik testlar va sinf tajribalari o'tkazildi. Imlo ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun fonetik mashqlar, ko'rgazmali diktantlar, interaktiv imlo o'yinlari va xatolarni tuzatish faoliyati kabi bir nechta o'qitish yondashuvlari qo'llanildi. Tadqiqot davomida metodlar qo'llanilishidan oldin va keyin ma'lumotlar yig'ildi va natijalar tahlil qilindi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, interaktiv va ko'rgazmali metodlarning tizimli qo'llanilishi o'quvchilarning imlo savodxonligini sezilarli darajada oshirdi. O'quvchilar imloviy andozalar, so'z tuzilmalari va tovush-harf munosabatlariga e'tiborliroq bo'la boshlashdi. Qiziqarli va takroriy mashg'ulotlar orqali to'g'ri yozuv mustahkamlandi va o'quvchilarda yozma ifoda borasida ishonch uyg'otildi.

XULOSA: Ona tili darslarida fonetik anglash, takrorlash va interaktiv metodlarni uyg'unlashtirish orqali imlo savodxonligini samarali oshirish mumkin. O'quvchilarning rivojlanish darajasiga mos yondashuvlar ularning imloviy bilimlarini mustahkamlashda va umumiy til kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: imlo savodxonligi, boshlang'ich maktab, ona tili, yosh o'quvchilar, imloviy xatolar, o'qitish metodlari, didaktika, psixologiya, pedagogik texnologiyalar, tuzatish ishlari.

Iqtibos uchun: Najimova A.D. Ona tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining imlo savodxonligini oshirish. // Inter education & global study. 2025, №6. B. 59–66. (In Eng.)

Spelling literacy is a key element of language competence, formed in primary school. In the modern world, it is not just an indicator of general culture, but also the basis for successful study and career. Improving the spelling literacy of primary school learners is especially important, because it is during this period that the foundations of written speech are laid. Gaps that arise at this stage can significantly complicate further mastery of both the native language and other subjects. This work will analyze the psychological and didactic foundations of the formation of spelling skills, systematize the causes of errors and offer effective methods for teaching spelling in primary school [5].

The formation of spelling skills is a multifaceted and complex process that requires the active participation and coordinated development of many mental functions. Among them, attention, memory (visual, auditory, motor, logical), thinking (in particular, the ability to analyze and synthesize), and imagination are of key importance. A special role in this process is played by phonemic hearing, which allows differentiating phonemes and correlating them with the corresponding graphemes, and morphological analysis of the word, which facilitates the conscious application of rules based on the morphemic structure of the word.

In the context of psychological and pedagogical approaches to skill development, the concept of the stage-by-stage development of mental actions developed by P. Ya. Galperin acquires particular relevance. According to this theory, mastering an orthographic action begins with the formation of an orienting basis for the action, when learners understand the purpose and conditions of completing the task. This is followed by the stage of the materialized form of the action, where direct manipulation of material or materialized objects occurs (for example, working with cards, diagrams). Then the action moves into an external speech form, when learners pronounce their actions out loud, comment on the application of the rules. And finally, the stage of the internal speech form comes, where the action is learned and performed mentally, becoming an automated skill [4].

An important aspect is awareness in the process of forming spelling skills. Mechanical memorization of rules without a deep understanding of their essence and logic does not lead to strong assimilation. Learners must understand why this or that word is written this way, see the connection between spelling rules and the morphological structure of the word, phonetic features of the language. Only conscious application of rules ensures flexibility and transferability of the skill to new language situations. The effectiveness of

memorizing spelling material is significantly increased by using different types of memory, which requires a variety of forms and methods of teaching.

Spelling is not a separate skill, but a part of language competence, closely related to its other components. It directly correlates with lexical literacy: understanding the meaning of words, including homophones, helps to choose the correct spelling. The richer the vocabulary, the easier it is to master spelling.

Knowledge of morphology (word structure) and syntax (sentence structure) is the basis for applying most spelling rules (e.g. spelling of endings, hyphenated or continuous spelling). Correct spelling makes the text understandable and expressive, while errors make reading difficult and reduce the culture of written speech. Thus, working on spelling develops the general culture of speech and communication skills.

For the effective organization of correctional work and the development of adequate methodological approaches, it is extremely important to understand the nature and causes of spelling errors. They can be divided into several groups. Psychophysiological reasons include the peculiarities of the development of the child's cognitive functions. Insufficient development of phonemic hearing often leads to the fact that the child does not distinguish subtle acoustic differences between sounds, which is reflected in writing (for example, mixing voiced and voiceless consonants).

Problems with spelling can be caused by several reasons. Psychological factors include poorly developed visual and motor memory, which makes it difficult to remember the spelling of words and reproduce letters correctly. Low levels of attention and self-control lead to mistakes due to inattention.

Linguistic reasons are related to the complexity of the Russian language: mismatches of sounds and letters (as in "корова"), numerous exceptions, homophones ("гриб" – "гипп") and homographs ("замок" – "замок") complicate writing. Insufficient knowledge of grammar rules (conjugation, cases) also directly leads to errors.

Didactic reasons are rooted in the organization of training. Ineffective methods, mechanical memorization, lack of systematicity, lack of practice and differentiated approach do not allow the formation of stable spelling skills [6].

Effective teaching of spelling is based on several fundamental didactic principles that ensure conscious and lasting acquisition of the material.

The principle of awareness suggests that learners should not just memorize rules, but understand their essence, logic and scope of application. A conscious attitude to spelling material promotes deeper memorization and the ability to transfer knowledge to new situations.

The principle of systematicity and consistency requires studying spelling rules in a strictly defined logical sequence, from simple to complex, taking into account their interrelation. A systematic approach ensures the strength of knowledge and prevents the formation of gaps.

The principle of clarity involves the wide use of various types of visual aids: tables, diagrams, reference signals, cards, didactic games. Visualization of spelling and rules promotes better assimilation and memorization, especially for young learners.

Finally, the principle of connecting theory with practice is key. The study of spelling rules should be immediately supported by a variety of practical exercises that allow one to practice and consolidate the acquired knowledge in real written speech. Only repeated and targeted application of the rules leads to the formation of a stable skill [8].

A wide range of techniques are used in the methodology of teaching spelling. The analytical-synthetic method is fundamental, assuming the analysis of a word with subsequent application of rules. To develop spelling vigilance, observation of linguistic phenomena and grammatical analysis are used, promoting conscious writing. The formation and control of skills are carried out through conscious copying and various types of dictations (preventive, explanatory), and vocabulary work includes systematic mastery of unverifiable words.

The efficiency of training is increased by introducing modern educational technologies. Game technologies (didactic games, crosswords) make the process more exciting and activate the cognitive activity of learners. Information and communication technologies (ICT), such as interactive whiteboards and online simulators, provide visualization, a variety of tasks and instant feedback. In addition, problem-based learning is used, developing independent thinking and project activities, involving learners in the creation of their own educational materials. Health-saving technologies ensure maintaining efficiency and concentration.

The effectiveness of developing spelling literacy directly depends on the quality planning and organization of native language lessons. Systematic work on spelling, its inclusion in each lesson, regardless of the main topic, is key. The principle of integration is important, in which spelling is closely linked with phonetics, morphology and syntax, as well as a differentiated approach, allowing you to adapt tasks to different levels of student preparation.

The basis for developing strong spelling skills is a diverse system of exercises. These can be exercises on applying rules (inserting letters, choosing options, forming words), on developing spelling vigilance (finding and correcting errors, copying with the highlighting of spelling), as well as creative tasks (writing texts, essays, written retellings with subsequent analysis of spelling).

Systematic diagnostics allows for timely detection of gaps. It includes control dictations, copying, testing and observation of written speech. Deep analysis of errors with their classification (by rules, vocabulary words, omissions) helps to identify typical and individual difficulties. Corrective work should be targeted and differentiated, including individual/group lessons, special simulators and keeping personal dictionaries of errors.

Effective interaction between school and family is the key to improving spelling literacy. It is important to constantly inform parents about the child's progress and problems, as well as to advise on organizing homework and using auxiliary materials.

Active involvement of parents in joint practice (reading, word games, checking assignments with self-correction) will enhance the results of school learning.

Improving the spelling literacy of primary school learners is a complex, multifaceted and continuous process that requires an integrated approach and systematic, targeted work on the part of the teacher. Achieving success in this area depends not only on the mechanical memorization of rules, but also on the formation of a conscious attitude to the language, the development of linguistic intuition, the improvement of analytical and synthetic skills and effective self-control. The use of various methodological techniques, including both traditional and innovative approaches, the active use of modern pedagogical technologies, as well as consistent individualization and differentiation of training allow us to create optimal conditions for the formation of strong and sustainable spelling skills.

Constant improvement of spelling teaching methods and their adaptation to the individual learners needs is extremely important. Taking into account the psychological characteristics of primary school age ensures the effectiveness of the process. Such a comprehensive approach allows spelling literacy to become an organic part of the child's linguistic personality, contributing to its successful development and confident written communication. Further research can be aimed at studying neuropsychological approaches to the correction of dysgraphia and the development of new digital tools for the formation and correction of spelling skills.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI | СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ | REFERENCES

1. Aidarova L. I. Psychological Problems of Teaching Primary School Learners Russian. – M.: Moscow State University Publishing House, 1978. – 216 p.
2. Bogoyavlensky D. N. Psychology of Spelling Acquisition. – M.: Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the RSFSR, 1957. – 348 p.
3. Vartanyan E. A. Journey into the World of Words. – M.: Education, 2007. – 176 p.
4. Galperin P. Ya. Psychology of Thinking and the Theory of the Step-by-Step Formation of Mental Actions // In the book: Reader on General Psychology. Psychology of Thinking / edited by Yu. B. Gippenreiter, V. V. Petukhov. – M.: Moscow State University, 1981. – P. 222–230.
5. Grigorieva M. A. Methods of Teaching Spelling in Primary School. – Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2003. – 224 p.
6. Jedek P. S. Spelling Problems and Ways to Solve Them. – M.: Education, 1975. – 128 p.
7. Jeltovskaya L. Ya. Formation of Spelling Skills in Primary Schools. – M.: Education, 1987. – 144 p.
8. Lvov M. R. Fundamentals of Methods of Teaching Russian in Primary Schools. – M.: Education, 1988. – 300 p.

9. Ramzaeva T. G. Methods of Teaching Russian in Primary Schools. – M.: Education, 2000. – 320 p.

10. Ushakova O. D. Vocabulary words: 1–4 grades. – St. Petersburg: Litera, 2007. – 64 p.

MUALLIF HAQIDA MA'LUMOT [ИНФОРМАЦИЯ ОБ АВТОРЕ] [AUTHORS INFO]

✉ **A.D. Najimova**, Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent v.b. Ajiniyoz nomidagi Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti, [**А.Д. Наджимова**, доктор философии (PhD) по педагогическим наукам, исполняющий обязанности доцента Нукусский государственный педагогический институт имени Ажинияза], [**A.D.Najimova**, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), in Pedagogical Sciences, Acting associate Professor Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz]; manzil: Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi, Nukus sh. P.Seytov ko'chasi; [адрес: Республика Каракалпакстан, город Нукус, ул. П. Сейтова] [address: Republic of Karakalpakstan, Nukus city, P. Seytov Street]